

A LOOK AT THE CREATIVE PATH OF THE PEOPLE'S ARTIST OF UZBEKISTAN

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Habibakhanim Ahunova

Karim Yuldashev

Mamlakatkhon Juraeva

Fergana regional branch of Uzbekistan state institute of arts and culture

Abstract: *This article covers the career of People's Artist of Uzbekistan, talented singer of Uzbekistan Habibahonim Ahunova.*

Keywords: *Theater, play, song, composer, image, character, stage, sound, performance.*

Habiba Ahunova was born on January 10, 1943 in Asaka district of Andijan region. She has been interested in singing since she was very young. The young talent will take part in various competitions and will be noticed by teachers. One such teacher was Gulomjon Rozibaev. Because Habibakhanim's pleasant voice and cheerful lips did not leave the talented composer indifferent. Gulomjon Rozibaev always supported Habiba's interest and tried to bring her up as a real singer. She won the respect of the people by participating in amateur art circles. She was called "Bulbulcha" by her classmates.

Habiba's ringing voice startled everyone. A 7th grader is invited to the Asaka City Theater. Habiba Ahunova, who took an active part in the People's Theater, became famous for her song "Shahlolaring". Fans were asked to sing the song over and over again. It was a great honor for the student. Habiba Ahunova graduated from high school in 1959. At that time, his name was well known in Andijan. He even caught the eye of a great artist like Abbas Bakirov. As a result, Habiba Ahunova was invited to work at the Andijan Regional Musical Drama Theater named after Y.Akhunboboev (now A.Bakirov). Habiba Ahunova worked in the theater from 1959 to 1963, performing a number of roles, singing beautiful and unique songs. Her first role was as Silver in "Zarafshan qizi". She won the applause of the fans for this role. As a result, she was given new roles. For example: Zulfiya in "Vatan ishqi", Karomat in "Toshbolta oshiq", Oyparcha in "Nodira" won the trust of teachers and the love of the audience. In 1963, Habiba Ahunova came to work at the Namangan Regional Theater named after Alisher Navoi. The theater, which has trained dozens of master artists, has become a real celebration of the development of Habiba Ahunova's art. Habiba Ahunova showed her true talent at the Namangan Regional Musical Drama Theater. With the sound of a bell, she made a lot of noise.

Habiba Ahunova has grown up to be an intense, pleasant, and easy-to-perform singer who will entertain fans of the art of singing. The pleasure of singing inspires Habiba Ahunova to new creative flights. She was passionate about creating songs that would be popular and captivating. She was not afraid of anything along the way. Another happiness of Habiba Ahunova is that at the Namangan Theater she was brought up by such a well-known composer as the Honored Artist of Uzbekistan Karimjon Mansurov. She worked hard, searched, practiced, studied the songs created by the teacher and tried to perform them to the rhythm. Habiba Ahunova is an artist who has opened a new school of Uzbek national performance. We have a lot of good women. But there is very little that can reach Habibahonim. Habiba Ahunova composers F.Sodikov, K.Mansurov, E.Kholmiraev composed melodies Saida Zunnunova's "Barno yigit", S.Qoriev's "Nayning navosi", A.Polat's "Namangan", "Ona yurtim", "Kormagan bo'lsam seni", H. Azimi's "Kongil ", D. Fayzi's "Sabo bilan", S. Hasanova's "Oshnoliging", "Odob bilan". Nobody can listen to the song "Alla" by M.Koriev and K.Mansurov performed by Habiba Ahunova. This song evokes the most delicate feelings of the human heart. This song is indescribable.

Uzbek musical drama is a multidisciplinary field of art, which is a combination of drama, music and theater. As a result of skillful staging, two major sources - music and drama - combine to form a whole, harmonizing and achieving the ideological and artistic goals of the playwright and the composer. This field of art requires a lot of talent from the artist. Not everyone deserves people's recognition. There are only a handful of such lucky artists. One of them was Habikhanim Ahunova. Gulnara in the musical fairy tale "Yoriltosh" by Sh. Sadulla, Sh. Azizahon in the lyrical drama "The heart given in youth" by Fatkhullin and B. Sobirov, Shakar in the musical comedy "Son of a Millionaire" by H.Islamov, J.Teshaboev and K.Mansurov, A.Tadjibayev, K.Mansurov's "Toy bola", K.Yashin in the musical comedy "Nurkhan" by T.Jalilov, Nurkhan in the musical drama "Nurkhan" by T. Jalilov, Kimmat in the musical drama "Rustam" by Sh.Jalil in the musical drama "Anvar ila Rano" in the musical drama "Layli and Majnun" by Rano, Sh.Khurshid, Glier and T.Sadikov Mehri in Khairullaev's comedy "Ketar jafosi", Risolat in A.Tursun's drama "Unforgettable days", T.Rahimova, M.Yusupov's Hundreds of characters like Sanobar in the musical comedy "Goodbye" are immortal masterpieces of Uzbek theatrical art. The actress has created wonderful images not only in national drama, but also in the works of foreign playwrights. Ophelia in Shakespeare's Hamlet, Desdemona in Othello, Amal in Sohibjamol's Gulisiyoh, Amalia in Schiller's The Thieves, Dino Vasnadze, A.Zayniddinov, K.Asom in V.Kandelakin's drama "24 Hours". In the musical drama "A thousand lovers for a girl" by Majidov and D.Soatkulov Lochi, Sohib Jamol, in the musical drama "Broken jug" by M.Mahmudov Omina, Urdibodu and in the musical drama "Bride of five sums" by S.Rustam Noznoz and others. plab roles showed how high Habiba Ahunova's performance potential was. Having established her own school of performance in

Uzbek theater and music, Habibahonim Ahunova was awarded the title of "Honored Artist of Uzbekistan" in 1972 and the People's Artist of Uzbekistan in 1975 titles were given.

Unique actress and singer Habiba Ahunova died on September 10, 1994 from a serious illness.

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